

Deliverable 7.2

Monitoring and Evaluation Framework and Tools

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Statement of
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1. INTRODUCTION

This is an intermediate document explaining the **operationalization framework** of the **Theory of Change for five of the six pilot initiatives targeted by T-Factor, namely Aleksotas Kaunas, Amsterdam Science Park, Trafaria in Lisbon, MIND Milan, and Zorrotzaurre Bilbao**. The objective is to build a monitoring and evaluation framework, with clearly defined output indicators and outcomes through data collection, analysis, and interpretation methods, based on the Theory of Change and data harvesting tools.

As mentioned in D4.3. Scoping and Ideating Tools and D7.2 (intermediate) M&E Framework and Tool, the operationalization of the Theory of Change across the pilots is encapsulated within the scoping & ideating stage in T-Factor, which uses the Theory of Change canvas to describe the link and logical sequence of the inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts of the temporary uses conceived and run by the pilots, to finally end up with a generalized impact framework.

To better comprehend the operationalization of the Theory of Change, it is important to highlight that T-Factor is a complex project, mainly due to its large scale, the number and diversity of stakeholders involved at different levels and geographies, and the huge diversity in the type of regeneration initiatives addressed. Moreover, the project is essentially an “additional layer” of activities that is plugged in the context of already existing agendas and roadmaps of redevelopments, that T-Factor aims to influence and transform on the long run – i.e. adjustments in the masterplan.

As mentioned in previous deliverables, the canvas has the following characteristics:

- Given that T-Factor is a complex project, we need a granular Theory of Change that is able to embrace diversity in the local strategies of temporary urbanism run by the pilot cities, while also maintaining consistency in the overall project's strategy. We also require a **narrative Theory of Change** able to support the process of thinking through impact **in terms of contribution rather than attribution**, and from the perspective of multiple voices. As also observed in previous research work developed by the project, the effects of temporary uses are hardly separable from the ones stemming from broader regeneration dynamics, and cannot be understood in isolation. Thus, we find it more meaningful to opt for a somewhat loose approach to the ToC and impact measurement that could better reflect the systemic character of T-Factor - i.e. looking at how an orchestration of temporary uses within a redevelopment can contribute to **mutually reinforcing, positive loops of change, and propel a diversity of benefits in the short and long term of urban regeneration**.

- It takes into account that T-Factor is a **multi-layered project** operating across **three main levels**: (1) the **mission level**, (2) the **pilot level** and (3) the **transnational level**.
- It is closely tied to the **six themes of the T-Factor General Impact Framework**, which are (1) Improving health & wellbeing, (2) Making places, (3) Attaining sustainability, (4) Growing prosperity, (5) Cultivating innovation and (6) Building communities.

Therefore, the scope of the ToC in the project is that of supporting systemic design of temporary uses while strengthening strategic reflection, learning and decision-making throughout implementation. Beyond that, it aims to support the **definition of indicators and evaluation processes** able to capture the contribution of temporary uses to regeneration outcomes and impacts - **beyond vanity metrics of pure outreach and engagement biased by the short term and uncritical reflections on what engagement and participation through temporary uses are made for**.

2. Methodology and tools

A. General Impact framework based on the Theory of Change on mission level

The operationalized Theory of Change (ToC) serves as a blueprint to think through and arrive at a pragmatic manner of measuring, assessing, and reporting on 'impact' in the broader context of T-Factor. This also involves consideration for the types of data that are required to measure and report on impact. To fully capture the objective of the ToC, a general impact framework is created which can be used, adapted, and applied by all the different pilot cities. The three key features of the canvas are the following:

- **Areas of KPIs measured and indicators:** the identification of some general KPIs / output indicators that could be used or measured after a meanwhile activity is identified, kickstarted or finalized. A meanwhile activity is a concrete way in which the local coalition can implement one or more of their missions and, consequently, try to achieve a desirable situation. The pilot city describes what they want to do, categorized in prompt activities (events, workshops, festivals, fairs - that will entail a prompt use of the space), regular use (activities with a regular/periodic use of the space), and stable use (activities that are settled 'permanently' in the area in the waiting time, such as, for example, artists residencies and more) (AAU, 2021). These activities will produce immediate, direct results/outputs.
- **Type of outcomes and outcome indicators/proxy (KTIs):** often, a set of direct outputs from an orchestration of different activities, could lead to an outcome over time.

Therefore, in line with the output indicators, a generalization of possible outcomes is identified that a pilot city can influence. The nine generalized outcome types are increased knowledge & awareness (1); new / improved skills & capacities (2); change in perceptions & attitudes (3); increased motivation and desire to act (4); enhanced access to resources/opportunities (5); enhanced & enriched relational capital (6); increased participation & collaboration (7), new/improved services, products and processes (8); and new/improved places (9).

- Impact themes:** The different outcome proxies depend on the impact the local coalition wants to contribute to in the medium and long run. The impact theme of T-Factor that is fulfilled by the missions i.e. the articulation of the six different themes on mission level. These impact themes are linked to several sub-themes (I-Propeller, 2021):
 - Attaining sustainability:** greening & biodiversity, efficient use of resources, energy transition / decarbonization, and air, water & soil quality.
 - Improving Health & Wellbeing:** physical & mental health, inclusion & equal opportunities, safety & security, and affordable housing.
 - Making Places:** sustainable & clean mobility, well-maintained, user friendly public spaces, local Identity & heritage, and integrated, connected, and multi-function places.
 - Growing Prosperity:** local enterprising, circular value chain, and employment & income.
 - Cultivating Innovation:** digitalization & light reindustrialization, learning, skilling, making, and creativity & talent.
 - Building Communities:** distributed power, agency & legitimacy, solidarity & belonging, urban commons, and cohesion & social justice.

Areas of KPIs measured	Output Indicator	Type of outcome (KTIs)	Outcome indicator/proxy (examples)	Impact theme
Activities	N. of sessions of activities delivered (e.g. specify if: N. of events, N. of trainings, N. of workshops...)	Increased knowledge & awareness	% of participants that declare to have improved knowledge.	Attaining Sustainability
	N. and diversity of topics addressed	New / improved skills & capacities	% of participants that indicate to have learned new skills. If there is an assessment moment – pass rate.	Improving Health & Wellbeing

Beneficiaries	N. of participants directly involved (by type)	Change in perceptions & attitudes	% of participants to indicate to have changed perceptions, feelings, and attitudes (better, same, worse).	Making Places
	N. of participants indirectly involved (estimated)	Increased motivation and desire to act	% of participants to indicate to have increased motivation and desire to act.	Growing Prosperity
Products	N. of tangible products of the activity	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	% of practitioners/participants that indicate to have more resources/opportunities available (financial, time, skills, etc.).	Cultivating Innovation
	N. of intangible products of the activity	Enhanced & enriched relational capital	% of participants to indicate to have enhanced trust and relational capital in the neighborhood / area.	Building Communities
Human resources	N. of experts involved	Increased participation & collaboration	# participants participating in co-creative activities % of participants who are open to participate and collaborate.	
	N. of operators/staff involved	New/improved services, products, and processes	# of new and/or different products / services / processes delivered.	
Stakeholders	N. of stakeholders involved (by type)	New/improved places	% of participants to indicate to that the place is improved.	

Figure 1: General impact framework for the Mission level based on the Theory of Change canvas.

B. Theory of Change in action: outcome mapping and output indicators on mission level

Outcomes are medium-term results attained or effects for individuals, groups, or issues, resulting from the direct output from the set of meanwhile activities (I-Propeller, 2021). Mostly, outcomes come in a sequence evolving over time, for instance the starting point often is the creation of knowledge and awareness (short-term), towards a shift in behavior (mid-term), aimed at achieving enhanced well-being (long-term). Figure 2 gives an illustrative example of this sequence (Clay, Collinge, Piazza, Noble, Corry, Davis, 2020).

Figure 2: Illustration of sequence of outcomes with the problem definition that mothers in a certain underprivileged area lack knowledge about the health effects of breastfeeding their infants.

As outcomes can be interpreted as a sequence of change over time, we have opted to use **outcome mapping (OM)** to assist the pilot cities. Outcome mapping is a methodology for planning and assessing projects, aiming to bring about sustainable social and environmental change. It is used for planning, monitoring, and evaluating development initiatives that helps a project team be specific about the actors it intends to target, the changes it hopes to see and the strategies appropriate to achieve these. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that the local coalition has the freedom to map the (forecasted) outcomes and to choose the meanwhile activities with the corresponding indicators, which illustrates the **bottom-up approach** that T-Factor is using for activities on the mission level. This approach gives the pilot city a sufficient level of flexibility and leeway, guaranteeing the uniqueness of each pilot city, as well as providing enough autonomy to brainstorm on activities and to adapt these during later stages of the project.

OM is the backbone of the T-Factor approach for the operationalization of the ToC and its granular definition for each pilot city. More specifically, the applied methodology envisages the following core steps (Martelloni, 2021):

1. Based on the general T-Factor's ToC, specific theories of change are developed with the pilot cities and their starting constellation of stakeholders. This step sets **the vision toward long term change and describes how a set of missions are meant to address problems and opportunities spotted**. To do so, we apply a combination of Theory of Change canvases specifically elaborated for T-Factor, whose goal is to help the pilot to conceive their missions and their strategies of temporary uses as connected to a broader logic, which takes into consideration the problems and opportunities previously mapped through research work, and the expected impact in terms of placemaking and regeneration. This information is already partly available when the local coalition is filling in the ToC canvas during the S&I activities.
2. In a second step, we dig deeper into the identified missions, defining the so-called **boundary partners** - i.e. individuals, groups or organizations with whom the missions, articulated through temporary uses and activities, will interact directly and with whom they anticipate opportunities for influence. This step starts to inquire logical connections between missions, boundary partners and impact themes.
3. Third, we define the **'progress markers'**, understood as **a set of statements describing a gradual progression of change in the boundary partner leading to the ideal outcome challenge**. As typically in OM, progress markers capture information that is relevant for monitoring purposes; in T-Factor, the role of progress markers is heavily pushed towards **strategic learning and decision-making**, as their observation and critical reflection over time is meant to guide the choice in temporary uses and boundary partners addressed. The local coalitions need to think through the following sentences, based on a **logic sequence of time and ambition**:
 - *What do we expect to see?*
 - *What would we love to see?*
4. Fourth, based on the preliminary outcome mapping, we **crystallize** the list of **starting pilot proxies** and **related targets**, and develop and tailor the specific set of **tools** for **outcome monitoring**, reporting and critical analysis for each pilot. The proxies in the framework are the **baseline of the objectives** that the local coalition wants to achieve. However, these are not set in stone as the activities of the local coalition can vary as well.

As already mentioned, an outcome could be a result of an orchestration of different activities. Therefore, the local coalition needs to think through possible output indicators directly resulting from its activities. The **identification of output indicators** is **crucial** since it will allow the pilot city to assess if the chosen activities could lead to the desired outcomes defined in the OM.

If not, the pilot city needs to redesign its activities or needs to rethink their defined and desired outcomes. The local coalition could measure and monitor all the predefined output indicators but has to assess if the indicator is significant for the activity and/or feasible to measure.

Importantly, the entry point of this process takes on different purposes from pilot to pilot, depending on the actual stage of design and development of temporary uses and activities. When these are already advanced as in the case of Amsterdam (where a preliminary list of activities was identified), the operationalization of the ToC through outcome mapping mainly served as **a tool to better refine existing plans and intentions, and to enhance synergies and reinforcing loops** between missions, activities, boundary partners and outcomes. Where this is not the case and there is no plan of activities in place yet, this process is heavily introductory to ideation, as it is meant to **inquire into which type of activities may hold the higher potential to address a set of outcome challenges, in connection with multiple impact themes, and for a diversity of boundary partners.**

The general impact framework adopted in T-Factor requires pilots to choose qualitative and quantitative indicators of their outputs and outcomes to enable assessing whether the targeted (orchestration of) meanwhile activities are successful. Besides being accurate related to the objectives, the indicators will be based on the following criteria:

- Having a **balanced mixture** between **qualitative** and **quantitative indicators**: Qualitative indicators look for diversity in different personal expressions or preferences, collecting the data from a small group. While quantitative indicators use a number/metric to compare the data with another moment in time, another situation or other project etc., collecting the data preferably from a larger, more representative group.
- Easily **measurable**: the determinants - (i) time, how long does it take to measure the indicator, ii) frequency, how many times per time period does the measurement need to occur iii) resources, the financial resources and how many people are needed, and iv) required skillsets and competencies of people needed to measure the KPI, - define if the indicators are easy to calculate. The local coalition will be responsible for the measurement on the ground.
- Easily **analyzable**: The data needs to be i) consistent and of sufficient quality, ii) translated to English if the data is gathered in a foreign language, and iii) analyzable in a time-efficient manner.

Figure 3: From a long list towards a short list of output indicators.

C. Theory of Change in action: output and outcome indicators for pilot and transnational level

While the definition of the desired situation and the outcome mapping on activity level / mission level is mainly coming from the pilot city itself (**bottom-up approach**), the **desired KPIs and outcomes** on **pilot** and **transnational level** is determined through a **top-down approach**. We have chosen this approach since the themes of pilot and transnational level are key to the project and must thus be followed by every pilot city to achieve the overall T-Factor objective. Furthermore, this approach allows us to make objective and effective **comparisons** across pilot cities. Moreover, it is important to notice that the indicators of the pilot and transnational level are

not yet finalized since the output and outcome indicators at mission level of the different pilot cities are not yet completed. The main objectives of impact on pilot level and transnational level are respectively:

- At pilot level, the pilot city wants to create change in the masterplan and the capacities of the developers. The spatial scope is broader with effects reverberating throughout the regeneration area and the wider urban context, both in terms of design (masterplan), people and developers.
- At transnational level, it wants to create change through raising awareness and creating knowledge of temporary uses in regeneration projects to other cities. The scope is no longer articulated in spatial terms, but rather considered as best or leading practice that may inspire others to take similar action.

Therefore, outcomes and impact for the various pilot cities are relatively the same and can be identified, analyzed, and monitored for the T-Factor project as a whole.

- At **pilot level**, same as at mission level, **outcome (KTI)** and **output (KPI) indicators/proxies** are used to describe, assess and eventually monitor the desired change the different pilot cities want to achieve. The features of the canvas are related to the three infrastructuring dimensions and corresponding sub-themes of the theoretical Theory of Change.

Strategic infrastructuring: the contribution of temporary uses to shared value creation around the real estate product			
Impact	Question	Output (KPI)	Outcome (KTI)
IMPROVED POSITIONING & REPUTATION	Are local identity, heritage & values valorized, and positive cultural and social evolution promoted? Is the visibility and reputation of the regeneration enhanced?	Positive change in perceptions, values, and meanings of heritage in the area	Increased reputation for cultural and heritage assets
RAISED ATTRACTIVENESS	Has the pilot city attracted new target groups over time and raised interest from different publics? Has it contributed to strategic partnerships and investment?	% of participants that indicate to feel attracted to the area after the visit (# of visitors to the area)	% of visitors that indicate open for a return visit (# returning visitors)
ENHANCED INTEGRATION, CONNECTIVITY & INTEROPERABILITY	Has it addressed broader objectives and challenges at city levels? Has it activated synergies with other initiatives in the city in addressing of shared & pressing challenges?	# of shared objectives with other regeneration projects in the city	1) # of synergy possibilities of meanwhile uses & local practitioners from other regeneration projects in the city 2) best practices transferred to other regeneration projects 3) Increased satisfaction of stakeholders concerning the cross-sectoral collaborations

Operational infrastructuring: the contribution of temporary uses to a resilient, multidisciplinary & integrated regeneration process			
ENHANCED & ENRICHED DESIGN & DELIVERY CAPACITIES	Has it leveraged and combined innovative skills & knowledge? Has it experimented with new ways of planning, designing, and delivering urban regeneration? Has it contributed to a new urban regeneration culture amongst developers and key regeneration stakeholders?	1) (Self-)identified improvement (tools) in capability and capacity to take action on 2) Number of different types of expertise leveraged	Enhanced capacity and competencies / expertise of local coalition and practitioners to leverage culture and heritage assets to deliver design-driven city-making approaches
ENHANCED RESILIENCE, FLEXIBILITY & ADAPTABILITY	Has it allowed to take more informed and evidence-based decisions? Has it transformed masterplans' assumptions over time in response to emerging needs and opportunities? Has it improved risk management tools and management?	# of project milestones and % of project milestones on track, in order to improve decision making	Project milestones and decision moments are integrated in a roadmap for the regeneration project, which is supported by all stakeholders, allowing developers to make better decisions regarding temporary uses
SHORTENED TIME TO IMPACT	Has it allowed to accelerate time to results and achievement of goals? Has it added on results and impacts that were not initially envisaged?	1) # initiatives to enhance positive (intended or unintended) impact of the meanwhile use and # of meanwhile uses which have the intended positive outcomes as expected 2) # of funding raised for activities	1) Forecasted outcome and impact accomplished faster than foreseen in the masterplan 2) Meanwhile activities receive sufficient funding to remain operational
Relational infrastructuring: the contribution of temporary uses to accelerating, expanding and boosting positive impacts towards the long term			
AUGMENTED RELEVANCE	Has it increased its capacity to address the needs and priorities of different people and groups, enhancing diversity and inclusivity?	# of different (regeneration) objectives/challenges tackled by # of different meanwhile uses	Increased percentage of permanent meanwhile uses compared to the initial masterplan
ENGAGEMENT DEPTH	Has it contributed to engagement of different publics? Has it uncovered novel ways of agency and collaboration?	# partnerships / collaborations created	Long lasting (strategic) partnerships
BOOSTED LEGACY	Has it created positive and long-lasting spillover effects? Has it unlocked new tools and approaches to urban regeneration?	Influence of policies	New policies to support the further development of the area, including financial and regulatory incentives

- The **transnational level** is anchored to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. Therefore, the SDGs can be profiled in connection to the different activities on mission and pilot level. Moreover, **three areas of KPIs**, other than the SDGs, are defined to track and monitor the creation of knowledge, practices and capacity through international collaboration, knowledge exchange in the field on a more short-term basis:
 - SDG profiling, specifically for T-Factor, SDG 11 and 17 receive a central place as they are the core goals of the project, contributing to sustainable cities and communities, and to strengthen international partnerships.
 - # SDGs targeted through cross-sectoral collaborations.
 - Knowledge exchange events realized.
 - # external initiatives hosted.
 - # city officials engaged.
 - # media partners activated.
 - Knowledge and practical resources created, made available and accessed.
 - # stories created.
 - Metrics regarding IT-platform of T-Factor.
 - Number of innovative new regeneration projects with a direct or indirect link to temporary uses.
 - # cities experimented with innovative methods of city-making and valorization of the waiting time in urban regeneration.
 - # twinning agreements signed by city mayors for international collaboration in the transformative waiting time.

D. Measuring systems

To monitor the pilot cities on the long run, T-Factor needs an **effective measurement system** for the defined output indicators and the desired outcomes regarding the different T-Factor layers. The choice of measuring system depends on various characteristics:

- A **qualitative indicator** demands **another measuring system** than a **quantitative indicator** – see data type in the table below.

- The measurement system needs to be **easy to implement**. Process tracing for example, which is finding out which process or mechanism exactly causes a certain result and impact, test whether the theory also occurs in practice, or whether there are alternative explanations for certain effects, is too difficult to implement. Therefore, a local coalition could opt for an interview.
- The **participation** of the **local coalition**. The effective measurement will be on the ground/area, therefore involvement of the local coalitions with the different actors and stakeholders is strictly necessary.

The list of different measurement systems that could be used by T-Factor are listed in the table below.

Name	Description	Reason to opt for measuring system	Data type
Survey	A survey or questionnaire is a series of questions that are asked to a certain group (or have them ask you) to obtain specific information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Quickly survey many people. ✓ Easily retrieve information about attitudes, preferences, and factual data (gender, age...). ✓ Easy to carry out and analyze, especially digitally. ✓ Possibility to ask closed and open questions. ✓ Useful to aggregate or compare data from different groups or periods. 	Both
(Group)interview	An interviewer enters a conversation with someone or a group of people.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Want to question a relatively small group of people in depth. ✓ By asking open questions and supplementary questions, you often get valuable, unexpected, and detailed information. ✓ Are complementary to quantitative data: find out, for instance, why people choose a survey or scale in a certain way. ✓ Get non-verbal information. ✓ With group interviews / focus groups, you collect a lot of reactions relatively quickly. If you expect that participants will influence each other's answers, you are better off with individual interviews. 	Qualitative
Track and analyse figures	If the effect that is aimed for can be measured, the process of analysing data and figures can be kickstarted. (e.g. increase of green spaces) and you can start analysing data and figures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ If the data is objective and figures are unambiguous. ✓ Can immediately start working with the data that you already have, allowing to make simple analyses quickly and with limited resources. ✓ Link existing databases to each other, so that at subsequent measurement moments you can access the data more easily. 	Quantitative

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ If there are data analyses carried out at regular intervals, this method eventually allows arriving at greater insights. ✓ Figures can easily be represented visually. 	
Document analysis	Collection of impact data from existing documents (usually about the history of activities, services, and the organization as a whole).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ When there is a lot of information about the (other) interventions that can easily be analyzed. ✓ Document analysis is relatively cheap and easy to organize. ✓ Since the basic documents are often for internal use, the information is credible and reasonably unambiguous. 	Both
Observation	Observe people, places, or interventions, or have them observe you, - directly or via visual material.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Get direct, tangible impact information. ✓ Data is relatively easy to collect. ✓ See and experience in concrete terms what the effects of the intervention are. 	Both
Expert analysis	In this method, someone gives expert advice on the intervention or impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientifically underpin the theory of change. ✓ Want to provide a methodological basis for data collection. ✓ If the subject requires technical expertise only a domain-/ or sector-expert can measure and know. 	Qualitative

3. Theory of Change in action: mission level

A. Aleksotas Kaunas

The Kaunas pilot aims to develop the Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park (AIIP) as a new yet integrated part of the city by focusing on **three different missions**:

- **Mission 1:** Collaborative, creative & community-led meanwhile: this mission aims to support wide involvement and engagement of local communities and stakeholders through temporary uses.
- **Mission 2:** people and planet-centered innovation ecosystem: this mission provides the resources and opportunities for a rich network of different key actors, such as research communities, start-ups and enterprises, with a particular focus on shared goals of sustainable development on technology, health and sustainability i.e. R&D, biotech, biofood, medtech, healthtech, and automotive directions.
- **Mission 3:** short distance and multi-function place: this mission creates and enables conditions for the development of new services and facilities on site that can contribute to the sense of belonging, livability, and creativeness of the area. The goal is that AIIP can be perceived as a short distance and multifunctional place.

The meanwhile strategy targets **multiple stakeholders** such as R&D actors, real estate actors, start-ups, enterprises (incl. businesses; cultural/event organizations), students, researchers, citizens, local communities, and policymakers.

The three missions are significantly aligned with each other. Focus on a collaborative, creative & community-led environment by planning engagement activities (mission 1), will activate relationships between different actors, which will be the foundation of a people and planet-centered innovation ecosystem i.e. partnerships and network ecosystem in biotech and other innovative solutions (mission 2). Lastly, the innovation ecosystem and community activities will contribute to a new identity and the creation of functions to the area (mission 3).

It aims to unlock **positive results/outcomes** such as increased creativity and talent (i), enhanced participation between various stakeholders (ii), increased knowledge and awareness of a people and planet-centered innovation system (iii), improved and connected place (iv), enhanced access to resources and opportunities (v) and other outcomes. The pilot city has an effect on several **impact themes**, such as making places, growing prosperity, cultivating innovation and building communities.

Mission	Outcome Type	Impact Contribution	Actor Type	Actor / Beneficiary Description	Pilot Proxy	More qualitative change associated to the quantitative indicator	
						What we expect to see	What we would love to see
Mission 1: Collaborative, Creative & Community-led meanwhile	Increased knowledge & awareness	Creativity & Talent	Other	Businesses; Cultural/event organizations; Tech related companies; Citizens of Kaunas; Local community	% of stakeholders that indicate to have better knowledge on how temporary uses could enhance the creativity and talent of people	A broader understanding of meanwhile uses / temporary urbanism, its positive application regarding impact and its actual application as a method in the creative process.	Continuously on-going meanwhile uses and various activities, which involves different actors, topics, and stakeholders.
	New / improved skills & capacities	Learning, Skilling, Making	Other	All relevant stakeholders (incl. Businesses; Cultural/event organizations; Tech related companies)	% of informed/mapped/engaged stakeholders that indicate to have better skills and capacities in collaborative and participatory placemaking	The AIIP is starting to develop a variety of well-established meanwhile spaces, giving the chance to stakeholders to learn and skill – i.e. implementation of collaborative and participatory placemaking meanwhile uses.	There exists a culture and practice on innovative city making methods through meanwhile uses. Furthermore, a proliferation of meanwhile initiatives that, starting from the experience of the AIIP, can scale across the city. Other enterprises could learn from the best practices of others.
	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Creativity & Talent	Other	Cultural/event organizations; Citizens of Kaunas; Local community; Businesses; Tech related companies;	% or # of citizens & cultural organizations that perceive increased collaboration between cultural, tech and business organizations etc.	The AIIP start to be perceived as a place where cultural, business and tech related actors start engaging with each other. Furthermore, stakeholders are more aware and have more knowledge on how to run and maintain local urban commons.	AIIP generally reported across media and public narrative as a place of (social) innovation. Furthermore, stakeholders perceive AIIP as an area where urban commons are present.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Local enterprising	Other	Businesses; Cultural/event organizations; Tech related companies; Citizens of Kaunas; Local community	1) # new planned/implemented activities 2) # participants in these new co-creative activities	New collaborations are starting to appear, which result in implemented meanwhile uses. Furthermore, community has enough room for their needs.	Collaboration between the indicated stakeholders materializes through meanwhile uses/activities. Furthermore, the AIIP is well integrated part of the city physically and emotionally.
Mission 2: People and planet-	Increased knowledge & awareness	Local enterprising	Business	R&D actors, start-ups, enterprises	% of informed/mapped/engaged stakeholders that declare to have improved knowledge on a people and planet-centered innovation ecosystem	A broader understanding on how meanwhile activities can contribute to people and planet centered innovation ecosystem.	Continuously on-going meanwhile uses and dissemination of knowledge regarding people and planet centered innovation systems.

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centered innovation ecosystem	Increased motivation and desire to act	Local enterprising	Business	R&D actors, start-ups, enterprises	% of R&I actors that show increased motivation and desire to locate themselves in the area (% of informed stakeholders showing interest activities in AIIP)	The AIIP attracts R&D actors, as they have increased motivation to locate themselves at the park.	As an R&D actor, it is highly rated that you're settled/placed in the AIIP (linkage with Silicon Valley).
	Increased participation & collaboration	Learning, Skilling, Making	Academia	R&D actors, start-ups, enterprises, students, researchers, citizens	# of diverse R&D actors collaborating to shared R&D initiatives in relation with Academia	Collaboration with academic institutions.	Constant collaboration with academia that supports knowledge/research exchange. Furthermore, high employment of program graduates.
	New / improved services, products, and processes	Employment & Income	Business	R&D actors, start-ups, enterprises, citizens	# of (increased) employment/income opportunities in the area through the attraction of diverse (R&D) actors*	The attraction of R&D actors, start-ups start to create job opportunities for various number of stakeholders.	AIIP is an area where multiple job opportunities arise through the sustainable settlement of R&D actors.
Mission 3: Short distance and multi-function places	Increased knowledge & awareness	Local Identity & Heritage	Community	Citizens of Kaunas	% of participants that report to be more aware of the existing heritage and identity	Stakeholders receive the chance to gain knowledge on the current and future identity of the area.	Meanwhile uses enrich the future identity of the AIIP.
	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Integrated, connected, and multi-function places	Community	Citizens of Kaunas	% of participants that perceive the area as more connected, attractive, and accessible	Increased perception of AIIP from a military base towards an innovation industry park.	AIIP identity perceived as an innovative and R&D hub, without forgetting its past/local heritage.
	New / improved places	Well-maintained, user friendly public spaces	Community	Citizens of Kaunas	# of (permanent) meanwhile spaces that are going to appear in the AIIP territory and its surroundings, that have a positive effect on the place	Effective and attractive meanwhile spaces within the AIIP territory and in the close proximity (e.g. Kaunas Fortress).	The area is relatively open for public and offers various urban amenities.
	Enhanced access to resources/ opportunities	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Other	All relevant stakeholders	1) % of participants that indicate to have more opportunities to access spaces, capacities, and funding for collaborative and community-led initiatives in the area 2) # of funding allocated to community meanwhile initiatives	Accessible funding raised for existing/ new meanwhile activities.	Easily accessible funding streams.
	New / improved services, products,	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Government	Policy Makers, real estate actors, citizens	Guidelines for legal framework supporting meanwhile spaces and uses (since legal framework is not there)	Guidelines that are introduced to a broad number of municipalities & decision makers in the country about	Proof of concept scaled at national level and replicated in other redevelopments.

	and processes					meanwhile uses. Furthermore, possibilities to improve and apply the framework to different places.	
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* The use of this proxy is tentative, as it will be potentially used after the mid-term review.

B. Amsterdam Science Park

The Amsterdam pilot tackles the challenge to renew the relationship between humans and nature in the Amsterdam Science Park (ASP) and its surroundings, by focusing on **three different missions**:

- **Mission 1:** Wild and cultivated spaces: this mission seeks to enhance green and wilderness-centered placemaking and visioning by leveraging arts practices to advance novel forms of understanding and appreciation of the living (green) environment and its multiple species.
- **Mission 2:** Do-it-together green practices: this mission aims to boost collaborative eco-practices to make ASP a lively place which supports sustainable, active, and green lifestyles that embrace nature and the living environment.
- **Mission 3:** Alternative (informal) masterplan: this mission focuses on an alternative masterplan, taking into account a plurality of actors on site - including non-humans -, with the ultimate aim to influence the complex governance structure of the site and enable more participatory forms of development.

ASP targets **multiple stakeholders** such as residents, students, local communities, the nature and other eco communities, policymakers, artists, and scientists.

The three missions have different objectives but contribute to bring the nature and humans closer together. Mission 1 focuses on steering novel visions and perspectives on nature and wilderness, while mission 2 emphasizes on community building and the creation of relational capital towards existing and emerging do-it-together eco-practices. Lastly, mission 3 is more transversal to the main objective of ASP since the alternative masterplan can be a mean to better connect eco-practices and green policy aspirations for the area and beyond.

ASP wants to stimulate **positive results/outcomes** such as increase knowledge and awareness on nature and biodiversity (i), new skills and capacities in eco-practices (ii), enhanced motivation and desire to adopt sustainable and green lifestyles (iii), increased participation and collaboration in the community (iv), enhanced access to funding (vi) and other outcomes. It influences the **impact themes**, improving health & wellbeing, making places, attaining sustainability, cultivating innovation, and building communities.

Mission	Outcome Type	Impact Contribution	Actor Type	Actor / Beneficiary Description	Pilot Proxy	More qualitative change associated to the quantitative indicator	
						What we expect to see	What we would love to see
Mission 1: Wild & Cultivated Spaces	New/improved places	Greening & Biodiversity	Nature	ASP Stakeholders/Nature	1) increase in square meter green gardens 2) Increase biodiversity in existing and new gardens (i.e. square meter highly biodiverse gardens)	Increase in plant biodiversity on existing plots and expand existing habitats for birds and other species.	A complex ecology with numerous red-listed species.
	Increased knowledge & awareness	Greening & Biodiversity	Community	ASP Stakeholders/Nature	% of participants that report to have enhanced awareness & value to green spaces and wilderness	Intervention (incl. eco-practices but also activities from arts and/or science) can increase awareness of added value of green spaces and wilderness.	Wild space is recognized and appreciated within ASP.
	New/improved places	Air, Water & Soil Quality	Community	ASP Stakeholders/Nature	Indicators related to soil quality	There is a measurement at a certain time of the period - to create visibility of soil/ground measurement and the importance of solid soil quality.	Stakeholders deploy regular measurement practices for biodiversity and soil quality. Furthermore, they take concrete actions regarding the results of the measurement.
	New/improved services, products, and processes	Integrated, connected, and multi-function places	Community	Existing and new Eco communities	# of new services and spaces in support to DIT eco-practices (ref. Informal Ecology Hub)	Multiple longer-period activities with artists, communities, stakeholders around ecology (no actual location) taking place in Amsterdam Science Park.	Semi-permanent glasshouse/pavilion where DIT green practices and small scale (viable) production landscapes, can be demonstrated, exhibited, and experimented with, attracting people from city, and eventually a flourishing, attractive permanent informal eco-hub.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Creativity & Talent	Business	Artists & Scientists	# collaborations with artists and scientists, nestled in the ASP	Artist partnerships will result that the existing places will be appreciated more.	Artist partnerships will result in collaborations with scientists, contributing to new & improved places.
Mission 2: Do-It-Together Green	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Cohesion & Social Justice	Community	Residents, students, local communities	% of people to feel more empowered to participate in the community/area - i.e. contribution to the different eco-practices (cohesion)	First interactions building between stakeholders and inhabitants through green practices (people getting to know each other through activities).	Self-running and a diverse mix of inhabitants & stakeholders around green practices (people working together autonomously).

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Practices	Increased participation & collaboration	Inclusion & Equal Opportunities	Other	ASP stakeholders and Academia	1) # different participants and partnerships in eco-practices 2) % of the participants that feel included with the different eco-practices	Short term relationships between stakeholders are set (i.e. first relationships).	Long term sustainable relationships are set between ASP stakeholders and Academia.
	Increased knowledge & awareness	Greening & Biodiversity	Community	Residents, students, local communities	% of participants that report to have more knowledge about biodiversity and urban ecology	Awareness of eco-perspective, learning to look at urban nature, understand relationships between living world (pollinators, plants, etc.).	More interest in eco-perspective and adoption of skills (starting to do urban gardening, participating in bird counting-type activities, understanding 'non-human' worlds (i.e. how does a bird experience the city?).
	Increased motivation and desire to act	Physical & Mental Health	Community	Residents, students, local communities	% of respondents that show increased motivation and desire to engage with eco-practices and sustainable and healthier lifestyles	There is more awareness on how engaging with nature by eco-practices. can positively influence mental & physical health.	Diverse engagement with eco-practices that noticeably improve mental/physical wellbeing.
	New/ improved skills & capacities	Learning, Skilling, Making	Community	Residents, students, local communities	% of participants that indicate to have gained skills in eco-practices	Local stakeholders have more understanding about the skills involved in eco-practices and starting to already improve (slightly) their skills and capacities of the practices.	Skills, knowledge, and practices learnt to be applied/goes beyond the scope of ASP - meaning the eco-practices are spreading in the city / other eco-practices will involve in the city.
	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Greening & Biodiversity	Nature		# of (new or shared) eco-practices initiatives	There are possibilities in the area where people can share their initiatives and gain an overview of active eco-practices.	There are new initiatives implemented in the area, seeding from other active eco-practices.
Mission 3: Alternative master-plan	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Community	Existing and new eco communities	1) % of practitioners/participants that indicate to have more opportunities to access funding/space 2) Enhanced access to funding & spaces for eco-practices	Accessible funding raised for existing / new green practices (collaborating with the community to get existing funding streams).	Easily accessible funding streams for green practices (collaborating with funders to create new/more streams).
	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Urban Commons	Community	ASP Stakeholders/Nature	Open and participatory forms of governance that include nature's right	T-factor pilot operates Proto-ZOOP; wherein the needs of both non-human and human actors are met within the activities, and/or local stakeholders are aware of ZOOP type governing	Semi-permanent eco-hub is governed through the ZOOP model. And local stakeholders establish as a ZOOP, and eventually implemented at top-level ASP governance.

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						structures (willingness to become a ZOOP).	
	New / improved services, products, and processes	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Other	Policy makers	Guidelines to improve policies embracing urban ecology and support to DIY practices*	Guidelines gain interest from relevant policy makers, active support from AMS urban ecology community.	Proof of concept adopted by ASP and could influence current and future policies.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Nature	Nature	Representation nature in addition to regular masterplan		
	New / improved services, products, and processes	Urban Commons	Community	ASP Stakeholders	# of features deployed & # users engaged on digital platform alt masterplan	Stakeholders and their communities know of and have visited the alternative masterplan digital platform.	The platform is out of beta and attracts users beyond the direct contacts of the Pilot project.

*Tentative: another possibility is to provide a policy framework.

C. Trafaria Lisbon

The Lisbon pilot leverages temporary uses to bridge the gap between the Academia and the local communities in the area of Trafaria, by focusing on **three different missions**:

- **Mission 1:** Shared, locally rooted identities: this mission aims the co-creation of a new identity to the area that acknowledges its rich past. It explores, socializes, and valorizes the multiple stories, community assets, and heritage that exists in the area.
- **Mission 2:** Innovative education & training: this mission seeks to develop educations and trainings in arts and technology in Trafaria. The main objective is to support capacity building and the development of skills, while attracting young and creative persons.
- **Mission 3:** Attractive & accessible area: this mission wants to improve the area by supporting the development of the place, access to new basic services and functions.

The **stakeholders** that the meanwhile strategy targets are students, residents in the area, local communities, cultural and creative industries, the municipality, and others.

The different missions are linked to each other. The first mission is transversal to the overall challenge of Trafaria – i.e. bring the academia and community closer to each other–, since it can change the perceptions of citizens and territorial stakeholders towards IAT@T and Trafaria itself, and creates eventually a shared, locally rooted identity across the area. Furthermore, by focusing on placemaking (mission 3) – i.e. creation of more connected places and more functions – the area will attract more stakeholders. Trafaria will provide learning opportunities to residents, students & other stakeholders and supports cultural and creative industries, which can generate new employment and income opportunities (mission 2).

Trafaria focuses on the creation of **positive results/outcomes**, such as more empowerment to collaborate with each other (i), a sense of belonging to the area of various stakeholders (ii), increased awareness and knowledge of local identity and heritage (iii), enhanced employment opportunities (iv), improved place due to relational capital but also accessibility and other services (v), and other outcomes. It contributes to the following **impact themes**: making places, growing prosperity, cultivating innovation, and building communities.

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Mission	Outcome Type	Impact Contribution	Actor Type	Actor / Beneficiary Description	Pilot Proxy	More qualitative change associated to the quantitative indicator	
						What we expect to see	What we would love to see
Mission 1: Shared, Locally rooted identities	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Solidarity & Belonging	Community	All the different communities (the different neighborhoods in the area)	% of participants that report to be more connected (to belong) to the area and community	People from the different communities start to feel connected to the area, through the meanwhile activities (big part of the activities is to try to increase the solidarity in between the different communities). Furthermore, first connections are being placed between the academia and the community.	The area is connected, there is a sense of belonging of the different communities in Trafaria. Furthermore, academia and the community are also connected.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Community	All the different communities	% of people to feel more empowered to collaborate in the community / area	People feel more confident / empowered to engage in activities in the area.	The empowerment by the people is a leverage point to disseminate empowerment to other communities in the area (snowball effect) - even in the larger region of Almada municipality.
	Enhanced & enriched relational capital	Solidarity & Belonging	Community	All the different communities	1) # different communities engaged with each other through the meanwhile activities 2) # problems mapped through the activities 3) % of participants that understand the argument of someone else	People of different communities are open to engage with each other with other "opinions", about potential problems of the area (remediation).	People respect each other and understand the opinion of others (Democracy) (they don't have to agree on each single topic).
	Increased knowledge & awareness	Local Identity & Heritage	Community	All the different communities	% of participants that report to be more aware of the existing heritage and identity	People are more aware and have more knowledge of the local heritage and identity of the area due to the meanwhile interventions.	People are engaging with the heritage and promote the identity of the area.
Mission 2: Develop innovative education & training	New / improved skills & capacities	Learning, Skillng, Making	Community	All the different communities	% of participants that indicate to have better skills and capacities in collaborative and participatory placemaking	People receive the tools / conditions / facilitation to improve its skills and capacities.	The community is self-educative - i.e. people are learning from each other and from themselves (develop their own methodologies to do things).
	New / improved skills & capacities	Employment & Income	Community	Students + residents	1) % of people that finish the education 2) # of projects (tools)	People are following the different education possibilities, linked to professional aspirations. Academic people enlarge the scope of its knowledge & methodologies facing the empirical needs of the	People have completed the education, indicating to have improved skills which can be used on the labor market. The academic qualifications will be embedded by the knowledge needed to develop the remediation actions of the project, which will

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						community. This will enable more employment opportunities, including entrepreneurship.	correspond to more employment qualifications & opportunities, and flourishing entrepreneurship & capacity building.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Creativity & Talent	Community	Students + residents	# participants and partnerships in co-creative activities to enhance creativity and talent (anticipated by academia)	New activities are created by the co-creative environment developed through the activities, the needs, and methodologies, involving citizens, academia, artists, and art companies.	The community has a new sense of talent capacities and of its powers and its possibilities in the labor market. This new community can develop new projects for the future and to increase the resilience against urban speculation.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Creativity & Talent	Business	Cultural & creative industries	# located cultural & creative industries	Same stated as above, but now for other stakeholders.	New businesses exist in the community - some of them in coalition - by the co-creative environment developed through the activities, the needs, and methodologies, involving citizens, academia, artists, and art companies.
	Enhanced access to resources / opportunities	Employment & Income	Community	Citizens	# of (increased) employment / income opportunities in the area	Develop prototypes through dynamic activities involving citizens, academia, artists, and cultural companies. This might lead to new opportunities and potentially new businesses / job vacations, motivating entrepreneurship.	New businesses exist in the community, involving an increase in job opportunities, but also new kind of job qualifications and products related to art, culture, and technology, directly connected with IAT programs and projects.
	New/improved places	Cohesion & Social Justice	Community	Citizens	% of participants to indicate that the place is improved through the social cohesion of the educative community/environment	The activities implemented in T-Factor have increased the levels of cohesion and mutual help between the different communities in Trafaria.	New dynamics emerged in the community, specifically through the outbreak of intercommunity products, services, projects, and small businesses.
Mission 3: Short distance and multi-function places	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Integrated, connected, and multi-function places	Community	Citizens	% of participants that report to perceive the area from an abandoned space towards an educative, connected hub	The articulation of T-Factor with Trafaria's urban regeneration masterplan and the emergence of IAT in this context has boosted the community projects with creative and innovative meanwhile spaces.	Trafaria has developed a new community identity, integrating new populations (namely the one directly related to the IAT development), new businesses and opportunities. IAT assumes to be a catalyst of these new social and cultural dynamics, enhancing symbiotic uses of art and technology to empower the community and emerging projects.
	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Well-maintained, user friendly	Community	Citizens	% of practitioners/participants that indicate to have more opportunities to access public spaces, capacities	Access to public areas of the IAT and surrounding buildings, including activities that foster participation and co-creation.	The area is well known as a place where communities have possibilities to access and use public places.

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		public spaces					
	New/improved services, products, and processes	Sustainable & Clean mobility	Government	Municipality	1) Creation of a multi-stakeholder committee with municipality 2) New services to access the area (physically & digitally)*	These type of services and provisions are still in discussion with the municipality but not yet finalized.	New digital and physical services in the area co-designed and co-created with the municipality.
	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Local Identity & Heritage	Community	Citizens	% of participants to indicate that the place is improved while maintaining the local identity of the area	Perception by the Trafaria communities that the IAT area and its transformation contribute to improving the area while maintaining the identity.	To have the IAT space & facilities as an open space that could be shared with the community both regarding the facilities (e.g., garden) but also the specific possibilities for interacting with researchers and artists.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Cohesion & Social Justice	Government	Municipality	# participants in co-creative activities (anticipated by municipalities)*	There are co-creating activities that we are currently in discussions with the municipality but not yet finalized.	Increased participation and collaboration in co-creation activities done with the municipality.

*Preliminary: depends on discussions with Municipality

D. Mind Milan

The overall challenge of MIND Milan is to create an open vibrant community and build a new identity based on nature, health, and wellbeing, by focusing on **three different missions**:

- **Mission 1:** Open, vibrant, and collaborative R&I ecosystem: this mission aims to create an environment where knowledge, skills, resources, and initiatives are being exchanged. More particularly, to disseminate scientific knowledge produced at MIND to the (wider) area and to bring in expertise of companies and organizations in the area.
- **Mission 2:** Active, healthy, and sustainable lifestyles: this mission wants to promote health and well-being through green practices and open-air activities to make the area a place of well-being and cultural references.
- **Mission 3:** Accessibility & usability: this mission focuses on making MIND a recognizable and accessible place.

The **target groups** of the meanwhile strategy of MIND are mainly local actors, such as residents, policymakers, local organizations and actors from the life sciences R&D field, both at the local, national and international levels.

Similar to the other pilot cities, the three missions are correlated to each other. Focus on the creation of a vibrant, and collaborative R&I ecosystem (mission 1), can stimulate a healthy and sustainable lifestyle, through education of the community and through recreational, creative and sport activities that put the challenges of a healthy and sustainable lifestyle into practice (mission 2). The temporary uses regarding the R&I ecosystem and a healthy & sustainable lifestyle attracts creativity and talents. These activities can contribute to reduce the perception of isolation of the area (mission 3) towards a more user-friendly, recognizable, and accessible place.

MIND wants to create **positive results/outcomes**, such as increased motivation to collaborate, engage, learn and skill from each other (i), the creation of new job and/or learning opportunities (ii), enhanced relational capital due to strategic partnerships (iii), enhanced motivation and desire to act to have a healthy, active and sustainable lifestyle (iv), increased accessibility of the area (v) and other outcomes. It influences the **impact themes**, improving health & wellbeing, making places, attaining sustainability, growing prosperity, cultivating innovation, and building communities.

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Mission	Outcome Type	Impact Contribution	Actor Type	Actor / Beneficiary Description	Pilot Proxy	More qualitative change associated to the quantitative indicator	
						What we expect to see	What we would love to see
Mission 1: Open, Vibrant and Collaborative R&I Ecosystem	Increased motivation and desire to act	Learning, Skilling, Making	Community	Local SMEs and organizations, start-ups, mind tenants (enterprises) and researchers and students	% of participants to be motivated to learn and skill with the array of opportunities of MIND	Participants to see and recognize MIND as a knowledge center open to all.	Cross-fertilization and regular exchange between local SMEs and organizations, start-ups and MIND tenants, researchers, and students (more autonomously).
	Increased participation & collaboration	Local enterprising	Business	Local SMEs and organizations, start-ups, mind tenants (enterprises) and researchers	% of participants to feel more empowered to collaborate in the community / area with regards to the existing initiatives - that can benefit MIND's presence	Stakeholders (i.e. local enterprises and others) in the area feel more confident / empowered to engage in activities in the area.	Local enterprises are empowered by the different activities, which is a leverage point to disseminate empowerment to other communities in the area - becoming a collector of international excellence and local expertise.
	New / improved skills & capacities	Learning, Skilling, Making	Business	Local SMEs and organizations, start-ups, mind tenants (enterprises) and researchers	1) % of participants that indicate to receive support in capacity building in their operations and foster adaptability 2) # tools and approaches to establish an open dialogue aimed at informing and thus, co-creating.	Participants learn to use new tools and approaches. Active and recurrent participation.	Community becoming proactive, co-creating, and managing activities.
	New / improved skills & capacities	Employment & Income	Business	New businesses (R&I businesses)	# of new businesses (R&I) that are willing to move to MIND	Increase in the number of businesses inquiring about collaboration with MIND. There is a growing interest in moving, to be part of the ecosystem.	Growing community of MIND not limited to stakeholders placed within the MIND site (not physically moving to the area). Community is growing due to for instance universities, not only business tenants.
	Enhanced & enriched relational capital	Creativity & Talent	Community	Local SMEs and organizations, start-ups, mind tenants (enterprises), researchers and students	# of partnerships developed in co-creative meanwhile initiatives	The activities implemented under T-Factor have increased the levels of cohesion and mutual help.	The activities implemented under T-Factor facilitate the creation of new partnerships between stakeholders in MIND and between local and MIND stakeholders.
Mission 2: Active,	Increased motivation	Physical & Mental Health	Community	Citizens, children, tenants, and Students	% of participants to indicate to have more motivation to have active and healthy lifestyles	People are more motivated, have desire to act towards a healthier and active lifestyle. Furthermore,	Participants adapt their behavior towards a more active and healthier lifestyle (i.e. for instance spreading the

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Healthy and Sustainable Lifestyles	and desire to act					participants become aware of the benefits of a more active and healthier lifestyle and trust scientific research.	word or following a healthy lifestyle, involving more people in the activities they do).
	Increased motivation and desire to act	Greening & Biodiversity	Community	Citizens, children, tenants, and Students	% of participants to indicate to have more motivation to have a lifestyle, which positively affect the planet	Participants gain awareness on the impact of their choices. Participants publicly define themselves "sustainable people".	Participants adapt their behavior, lifestyle, and purchase choices towards a more environmentally friendly one and advocate for sustainable activities.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Cohesion & Social Justice	Community		% of participants that indicate that the activities of T-Factor contribute to boost the engagement with the communities (i.e. community engagement activities)	Increased participation related to T-Factor events and other activities.	Some project ideas from MIND Education or from other stakeholders in the events become meanwhile uses and ultimately permanent activities.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Greening & Biodiversity	Community	Citizens, children, tenants, and Students	Increased % of participants to conference and other events of T-Factor (i.e. increased interest of community in active, healthy, and green lifestyles)	Resonance of environmental knowledge by citizens.	Increase the number of high-level students that choose scientific degree at University.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Solidarity & Belonging	Community	Citizens	% of vulnerable people involved and affected by the activities.	Broaden T-Factor activities to a wider spectrum of actors (different generations and social backgrounds, people with disabilities, associations, cooperatives, ...).	Co-creation and co-managing of open spaces, appropriation by most fragile and disadvantaged groups.
Mission 3: Accessibility & Usability	Change in perceptions & attitudes	Integrated, connected, and multi-function places	Community	citizens from surrounding municipalities	% of participants to have changed perceptions regarding alternatives of accessibility of the area	Local community involved in T-Factor activities and using the new accessibility ways to reach MIND and walk through it.	MIND becomes an attractive destination to be reached by surrounding communities, spontaneously with own slow mobility means.
	New/improved places	Well-maintained, user friendly public spaces	Community	citizens from surrounding municipalities	% of participants to indicate that the place is improved i.e. usability of the area. More functions and new uses	(Permanent) activities unlock new functions and uses in the area, attracting local community and citizens.	MIND is identified and chosen as venue for events and everyday activities by local citizens and authorities.
All missions	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Efficient use of resources		The districts and the surroundings	% of extra investment (in kind or funding) as a result of the T-Factor activities	Financial opportunities for new meanwhile activities	Easily accessible funding streams for the different meanwhile activities, with a distinctive funding strategy and program

E. Zorrotzaurre Bilbao

Fostering an innovative ecosystem between grassroots movements and Higher education institutions (HEIs) is the core objective of Zorrotzaurre Bilbao. It focuses on **three different missions**:

- **Mission 1:** Triggering collaboration: This mission focuses on activities such as joint programs and events that weave people in places, to boost collaboration between grassroots and HEIs. Diverse themes could be explored with the collaborations, for instance the development of a new curricula and education/training experiences, 'third' and hybrid spaces offering new services to various stakeholders and new pilot calls/projects for impactful businesses and commercial activities in the area.
- **Mission 2:** Collaborative & participatory governance: this mission aims to develop collaborative and participatory schemes of governance in the area.
- **Mission 3:** Enable regulation for meanwhile uses: this mission wants to assist the creation of a regulatory sandbox with regards to access of spaces that can be used to support and emerge initiatives inside and outside the island.

Grassroots movements, universities, businesses, cultural & creative actors, and others are the **stakeholders** the meanwhile strategy targets.

The priority of the pilot city is to enhance the community building in the area and to promote the collaboration innovation ecosystem in an environment where meanwhile uses are an asset for urban place-making with an active contribution of HEIs (mission 1). Furthermore, a collaborative & participatory governance (mission 2) and the creation of a more inclusive, resilient, and trust-based framework of regeneration (mission 3) are key factors for the success of the meanwhile activities in the regeneration project.

Zorrotzaurre Bilbao wants to stimulate **positive results/outcomes** such as increased knowledge and awareness of the opportunities and challenges of the regeneration project (i), new and improved services and products (ii), more learning possibilities (iii), enhanced engagement and partnerships (iv), a new improved governance model (v), a legal framework for meanwhile uses in the area (vi) and other outcomes. It contributes to the following **impact themes**: making places, growing prosperity, cultivating innovation, and building communities.

Mission	Outcome Type	Impact Contribution	Actor Type	Actor / Beneficiary Description	Pilot Proxy	More qualitative change associated to the quantitative indicator	
						What we expect to see	What we would love to see
Mission 1: Triggering collaboration	Increased knowledge & awareness	Solidarity & Belonging	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	% of the participants that indicate to have increased knowledge & awareness on the regeneration process and activities occurring in the area	Half of the participants will increase the knowledge of the regeneration project in Zorrotzaurre, ultimately influencing other stakeholders in the area.	All the participants have increased knowledge of the various topics (incl. opportunities and challenges) of the regeneration project. The knowledge of the grassroots movements and universities could disseminate outside the area.
	Increased knowledge & awareness	Learning, Skilling, Making	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	Increased knowledge & awareness on open innovation principles and approaches due to the collaborations	At least 6 organizations improving their collaboration skills and can create an innovation ecosystem, where they implement the gained knowledge into practice.	Furthermore, 3 lighthouse projects emerge where different actors could collaborate with each other in the near future. A lighthouse is a best practice of a project and/or enterprise where different actors feel stimulated to collaborate with.
	Increased motivation and desire to act	Solidarity & Belonging	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	% participants that indicate to feel motivated to collaborate and engage with each other	All invited participants of the open calls feel motivated to collaborate (only organizations of the grassroots initiatives located in in the island ZZ in scope).	A stable ecosystem of collaboration among all participants beyond the T-factor project.
	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Urban Commons	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	1) % of participants that indicate to have more resources available due to the mutualization of resources across the island 2) increase in # tools in shared used	People are aware that the resources and tools are available due to the collaborations. Therefore, 75% declare to feel to have more resources & tools.	Crystallization / materialization of the inventory. There is a well-structured inventory where people are not only aware but also engage in the creation of an inventory of shared resources and tools available in the island.
	New / improved skills & capacities	Local enterprising	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	% of the participants that indicate to have improved skills / capacities to scale up their business models and/or product development*	At least one of the funded projects to have the potential to scale up.	The project that has managed to scale up and can access an acceleration/incubation/ seed-funding program.
	New/improved services, products, and processes	Local enterprising	Community	Grassroots movements & universities	# increase of new / improved services, products, and processes, resulting from the open calls	Minimum of 3 new / improved services, products, and processes, directly coming from the open call proposals.	New products / services developed based on the results from a previous call or lighthouse project e.g. project proposals in call 2 is based from ideas and outcomes from proposals or implemented projects of the previous call. This will enhance the collaboration between different actors.

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	New / improved places	Local Identity & Heritage**	Other	Grassroots movements; Informal groups of citizens; other Cultural & creative actors	Perception of participants of T-Factor activities as a lighthouse for new urban development paths	Half of the participants perceives Bilbao Pilot's activities as good practices to prototype solutions in urban areas under transformation.	All the participants perceive Bilbao Pilot's activities as good practices to prototype solutions in urban areas under transformation, influencing a variety of different outcomes and impacts.
Mission 2: Collaborative & Participatory Governance	Increased motivation and desire to act	Solidarity & Belonging	Other	Businesses; cultural & creative actors; universities; authorities***	% of participants to have increased motivation and desire to engage in multi-actor dialogue and collaboration	75% of the participants have increased their motivation or desire to participate in a multi-stakeholder dialogue, involving businesses, cultural actors, and others.	All stakeholders participate in a stable and well-structured multi-stakeholder dialogue, creating a sense of belonging to ZZ.
	Increased participation & collaboration	Learning, Skilling, Making	Business	Businesses; cultural & creative actors; universities	# of learning possibilities due to the collaborative & participatory environment of the area	People start to engage with each other due to the co-creative environment developed through the activities, creating informal learning groups.	People are learning and skilling from each other and are able to develop new opportunities / projects for the future (self-learning).
	Enhanced & enriched relational capital	Learning, Skilling, Making	Business	All relevant stakeholders	# participants and partnerships in co-creative activities to enhance learning & skilling	A collaborative culture is beginning to be established among stakeholders to enhance learning & skilling (i.e. working towards private public partnerships that can take many forms).	Stakeholder partnerships are established in line with a collaborative governance model to enhance learning & skilling.
	Enhanced access to resources/opportunities	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Other	Businesses; cultural & creative actors; universities	Enhanced access to resources and other capacities (access to policymakers, funding, etc.) to plan and execute meanwhile uses	The new governance model improves accessibility and knowledge about resources and capacities for planning and managing meanwhile uses.	The new governance model integrates "meanwhile uses" into its strategy as critical activities to drive the island's urban transition process. These meanwhile uses have the feasibility/opportunity to transform to a permanent use. Ideally, after the T-Factor project, there will be new open calls without the resources of T-Factor.
	New/improved services, products, and processes	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Government	public authorities	New improved governance model	The new governance model generates knowledge hubs that foster and promote new businesses, products, and services.	The new governance model integrates all the stakeholders in its strategy to foster and promote new businesses, products, and services.
	Mission 3:	Enhanced access to resources/	Integrated, connected, and multi-	Community	Informal groups of citizens (neighborhood)	Enhanced access and use of the area through the meanwhile uses	Meanwhile uses unlock new functions and uses in the area,

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Enabling Regulation for Meanwhile Uses	opportunities	function places				attracting local communities and other stakeholders.	the chance to explore their (business) ideas.
	New/improved services, products, and processes	Distributed Power, Agency & Legitimacy	Other	Grassroots movements; Informal groups of citizens; other Cultural & creative actors	Legal framework for meanwhile uses the area Management / Municipality model in place for the meanwhile uses in the area	New models of municipal management are explored to facilitate the temporary uses of the "meanwhile spaces" of a regenerating urban area.	A new management model makes the access and use of "meanwhile spaces" easier, more flexible and transparent, integrating them into the city's urban development strategy.

*Preliminary: defining the activities to help the projects enhance the business models could be difficult, since there are a lot of different actors involved / to be coordinated. This means that results of this activity could not be solely the result of T-Factor. If not feasible, inspirational activities to successfully submit proposals, could be used as an alternative, to aim to increase the knowledge and skills of the participants. Furthermore, the local coalition will include the feasibility to scale up the prototype in the requirements of the proposal.

**Include heritage conservation and care for local identity in one of the calls. However, the proxy indicator used could also be valid for other impact contributions, such as sustainability, social inclusion, social innovation, or prosperity growth.

***Ideally, the proxy will be segmented in the different stated stakeholders. At the moment, possible segmentation is policy makers vs other stakeholders.

F. Euston London

Since the scoping and ideation activities need to start with a preliminary proof of concept of the portfolio matrix, activities of monitoring and evaluation could not kickstart. The activities, such as workshops to set a baseline of the outcome mapping for Euston London, will be planned after the review period and after the S&I activities.

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